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A VALIDATED SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF AMBROXOL HYDROCHLORIDE AND LEVOCETIRIZINE DIHYDROCHLORIDE IN TABLET FORMULATIONS

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ABSTRACT

A simple, precise and accurate spectrophotometric method was developed for simultaneous estimation of Ambroxol HCl and LevoCetirizine DiHCl in bulk and tablet dosage form. This method is based on use of Derivative method for simultaneous estimation of both the drug from tablet and Distilled water is used as solvent. Ambroxol HCl shows maximum absorption at 244nm and LevoCetirizine DiHCl shows absorption at 231 nm. Ambroxol HCL and LevoCetirizine HCl obeys Beer's law in the concentration range 0-32 ug/ml and 0-30ug/ml respectively. During estimation of Tablet no interference was found from excipients. The dosage form contains 60 mg Ambroxol HCl and 5 mg LevoCetirizine DiHCl. The suitability of this method for estimation of both drugs was proved by validation. Statistical analysis data shows that the developed method is sound under analytical condition and can be used for routine analysis of both drugs.

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INTRODUCTION

Ambroxol HCl is a derivative of alkaloid vasicine, also naturally obtains from *Adhatoda vasica*, is a potent mucolytic agent capable of inducing thin copious bronchial secretion. It is chemically 4-[[[(2-amino 3,5-dibromophenyl) methyl]amino]cyclohexanol Hydrochloride. Ambroxol is a metabolite of bromhexine.

Levocetirizine DiHCl is a second generation antihistaminic agent and chemically it is R [2-[4-[(4-chlorophenyl)phenylmethyl]-1-piperazinyl]ethoxy]acetic acid dihydrochloride. Levocetirizine is the acid metabolite from oxidation of the primary alcohol of the antihistamine hydroxyzine with marked affinity for peripheral H₁ receptor.

Literature survey reveals that there are reported methods for simultaneous estimation of both drugs by spectrophotometric, chromatographic. The proposed method is validated as per ICH guidelines.

Experimental method

Instrument

A Shimadzu model UV-VIS 1700 a double beam UV-VIS spectrophotometer with spectral bandwidth of 2 nm and wavelength accuracy of ± 1 nm with 10 mm matched Quartz cells was used. Electronic balance Afcoset FX 300 was used.

Pure Drugs and Lab Reagents

Gift sample of Ambroxol HCl and Levocetirizine DiHCl were procured from Cure Pharma Ltd. Pune. Double distilled water available in laboratory and reagents of AR grade were used. Formulation containing Ambroxol HCl 60 mg and Levocetirizine DiHCl 5 mg Brand Name Lorfast (Cadila Lesante Lab) were procured from local market.

Preparation of Standard stock solution

Accurately weighed pure drug powder equivalent to 20 mg of Ambroxol HCl and 20 mg of Levocetirizine DiHCl separately and transferred to separate 100 ml volumetric flask. Dissolved in water and volume was made up to 100 ml with water which produced 200 μ g/ml conc. of each drug.

Method: Derivative order method

Standard solutions each of 10 μ g/ml of Ambroxol HCl and Levocetirizine DiHCl were prepared in 10 ml volumetric flask and scanned in 200 to 400 nm wavelength range against water as blank. Absorption spectra of both drugs were recorded and the λ_{\max} of Ambroxol HCl and Levocetirizine DiHCl was found at 244 and 231 nm respectively Fig No.1. Series of standard solutions were prepared in conc range of 4 to 32 μ g/ml. and scanned in 200 to 400 nm range in spectrum mode on the spectrophotometer. Absorbance was recorded at 231 and 244 nm wavelength for CET and AMB and calibration graph was plotted.

Fig. No. 1 Simple overlain spectra of CET and AMB.

From overlain spectra Fig.No.1 both drug has absorption at 231 nm wavelengths hence to overcome the interference Derivative method was applied. Zero order spectra of both drug was converted to first order derivative spectra Fig No.2a and 2b. From overlain spectra Fig.No.3 244 nm was selected λ_{\max} of Levocetirizine DiHCl where no interference of Ambroxol HCl and 254 nm was selected as λ_{\max} of Ambroxol HCl as it was zero crossing of Levocetirizine HCl Both drugs obeys Beer's law in first order derivative mode Fig.No.4 at the respective wavelength.

Fig. No.2a. First order derivative spectra of CET.

Fig. No.2b. First order derivative spectra of AMB.

Fig. No.3 First order overlain derivative spectra of CET and AMB.

Analysis of Tablet Formulation

Twenty tablets were weighed and crushed to powder, powder equivalent to 60 mg of AMB and 5 mg of CET were weighed and transferred to 100 ml volumetric flask, powder was dissolved in water and volume was made up to 100 ml with water. Mixed well, Resulting solution was filtered through whatman filter paper. Aliquots of solution were diluted to 10 ml into 10 ml volumetric flask and solution was scanned and absorption of solution was measured at 244 and 254 nm. Fig No.5 Amount of each drug in solution was calculated and results are shown in Table No.1

Fig. No.5. First order derivative spectra of Formulation of CET and AMB

Table No.1.

Tablet sample	Label claim(mg/Tab)		% of Label claim estimated*		Standard deviation		Coefficient of variance	
	AMB	CET	AMB	CET	AMB	CET	AMB	CET
Sample I	60	5	99.96	99.39	1.1384	1.3959	1.1386	1.4047
Sample II	60	5	99.12	99.71	1.4571	1.3023	1.4700	1.3060

* Mean of six determinations.

Fig. No. 5 Simple spectra of Formulation of CET and AMB.

Validation of the Method

The method was validated as per ICH guidelines

Linearity

The linearity of an analytical method is its ability to obtain test results which are directly proportional to the conc of analyte. Series of standard solutions were prepared in conc range of 4 to 40 ug/ml. and scanned in 200 to 400nm range on the spectrophotometer. Absorbances of the standard solutions were recorded at 241 and 283nm in derivative order. Regression equations was summarised in table.

Precision

The precision study was carried out by performing assay of tablet six times. Also the reproducibility in result was studied by interday and intraday precision. SD and RSD show methods precision and summarised in table.

Accuracy

The accuracy of an analytical method expresses the closeness of an agreement between test result and true result. Accuracy study was performed by recovery study i.e. standard addition method. Diluted standard solutions of AMB and CET were prepared and standard solutions added in 80,100 and 120% proportionate. SD and RSD of triplicate study tabulated in Tab.No.3

Limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantitation (LOQ)

The LOD and LOQ of AMB and CET by the proposed method were determined using calibration graph method and calculated as $3.3\sigma/S$ and $10\sigma/S$.

Robustness and ruggedness

It is measure of capacity of analytical procedure to remain unaffected by small but deliberate variations in method parameter.

Table No.1: Optical characteristics and statistical analysis of the proposed method.

Parameters	Ambroxol Hydrochloride	LevoCetirizine DiHydrochloride
Wavelength (nm)	244 nm	231 nm
Beers law range ug/ml	0-32 ug/ml	0-32 ug/ml
Regression equation	Y= 0.032X	Y= 0.0254X
Correlation coefficient	0.9997	0.9999
LOD ug/ml	1 ug/ml	1 ug/ml
LOQ ug/ml	3ug/ml	2ug/ml
Accuracy	RSD 1.4850	RSD 1.3718
Precision	Repeatability*	99.18% SD 0.8164
	Intraday*	100.19% SD 1.4853
	Interday*	99.65% SD 1.7167
Robustness	± 2 nm	± 0.007
Ruggedness	Analyst 1*	99.658%
	Analyst 2*	100.21%

*Mean of Six determinations 100.19%.

CONCLUSION

The method is precise, accurate and reproducible after revalidation and routinely used for simultaneous estimation of Levocetirizine dihydrochloride and Ambroxol hydrochloride from combined formulation.

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